

Physical variables to shape individual interpretations into collective knowledge

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I am a design researcher completing a PhD that investigates how **material** and **participatory approaches** can support the articulation, interpretation, and communication of **embodied health experiences**. My research focuses on women's experiences of recurrent urinary tract infections and antimicrobial use, a healthcare context characterised by urgency, uncertainty, and repeated encounters with clinical systems. Emerging from my background in participatory design and **data physicalization**, and informed by **feminist and situated epistemologies**, this work addresses a persistent gap between lived symptoms and their clinical representation. While healthcare systems rely heavily on standardised descriptors, scales, and questionnaires, symptoms in this context are often experienced as composite, ambiguous, and difficult to articulate rather than as discrete events, which challenges their representation within existing data practices.

In this research, data physicalization is approached as a participatory and material practice through which embodied experiences are explored, articulated, and collectively interpreted, extending its role beyond the representation of predefined information. Central to this approach is the role of **physical variables**. In data physicalization, physical variables refer to material properties through which data can be expressed, such as size, weight, texture, density, and spatial arrangement. Rather than treating these variables as stable encoding parameters, my research positions them as **relational, situated, and interpretative qualities** that acquire meaning through the interaction of people, data, and materials.

Physical variables as generative devices constitute the main contribution of this research and are explored through participatory workshop sessions in which participants work hands-on with **Data-Probes**, introduced in this research as a set of **basic geometric forms produced in different sizes and materials**. The Data-Probes can be easily combined, rearranged, and compared, directing attention to material

properties such as weight, resistance, texture, and balance. By foregrounding these qualities, the probes support the exploration of how bodily sensations associated with symptoms can be expressed through interaction with materials. Their manipulation invites gestures such as assembling, positioning, and balancing elements, allowing sensations and affordances to guide interpretation and communication. In this context, the absence of prior making expertise proved beneficial, as participants explored the probes experimentally and negotiated meaning between data, bodily experience, and material affordances.

The **workshops** generated empirical results that support a more grounded discussion of physical variables in data physicalization. In particular, the research initiates **associations between specific urinary tract infection symptoms and recurring physical variables**, enabling a level of precision that is often difficult to achieve in general reviews of data physicalization projects, where variables are discussed abstractly or across heterogeneous contexts. At the same time, the **activity and materials**, formally presented as an **Apparatus**, are intentionally designed to adapt to contexts beyond healthcare. They are particularly suited to situations that require moving from subjective data and individual interpretation towards collective knowledge through debate and discussion.

For this occasion, I would share empirically grounded results from my research, including specific associations identified between symptoms and physical variables. Building on this material, I aim to contribute to discussions on the role of physical variables within data physicalization practices, drawing from participatory sessions where interpretation emerges through gesture and material exploration during the selection and assembly of components.

Figure 1 - Laser-cut plywood labels representing symptoms (left) and physical variables (right) used during the workshop.

Figure 2 - Collaborative discussion during one of the workshop sessions in which participants associated symptom and physical variable labels, forming a shared reference that later guided the manipulation and arrangement of materials.

Figure 3 - Artefacts 9 and 17 resulting from the assembly of Data-Probe components following the collective association of symptoms and physical variables.

More information on the research and the Apparatus is available at:
<https://ginevraterenghi.github.io/data-probes/physical-variable-apparatus.html>

How to read:

*methods
 *contributions